

The Impact Of Using Gamification On The Performance And Mathematical Skills Of Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University High Schools Students From Teachers Points Of Views

Mervat Abdullah Babeer

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 28, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Mathematical Skills, Teachers, Performance, Strategy</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4969334</p>	<p><i>Many studies have confirmed the effectiveness of the application of gamification in the education sector and its impact on the level of students' performance and achievement. (Al-Ghamdi, 2019), (Hamari & Koivisto, 2014) Therefore, this study aimed to discuss the impact of using electronic Gamification on the performance and mathematics skills of Princess Nora University High Schools students from teachers points of views. To achieve the aim of the study, the descriptive and analytical method was used by applying a questionnaire to 169 mathematics teachers as a random sample. The study concluded that there is agreement among mathematics teachers on the positive trend towards employing electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics and acquiring the skills of remembering, understanding, analysis, problem-solving and decision-making. Therefore, there is an impact of applying this strategy on the level of mathematics performance and skills of students, but there are still difficulties and obstacles represented In the necessity of training and qualification for the teacher and the student and the presence of necessary tools such as applications and internet connection in addition to the existence of applications commensurate with the established educational goals affiliated with the Ministry of Education so that the teacher can rely on In general, employing gamification applications helps students acquire mathematical concepts, remember and apply rules, overcome the difficulties of the subject and increase motivation towards it, solve the problem of individual differences between students and the existence of a positive motivation through the spirit of competition to learn skills.</i></p>

Introduction

Technological progress has led to the emergence of new educational methods and strategies that contribute to increasing students' motivation towards learning, and make learning more enjoyable, stimulating and interesting. Among these strategies, which have appeared recently and have spread widely, as the use of gamification has spread in various fields in various institutions, organizations and agencies, including universities and education sectors. (Shaheen, 2020)

Gamification originated as a term in the digital media industry, and its first use dates back to 2008, but the term does not see widespread adoption before the second half of 2010. Game design elements have been used in non-gaming contexts to stimulate and increase user activity, maintain learning speed and gain motivation to learn under the name of "gamification". Augmented reality games that use digital devices to keep pace with the environment surrounding the learner, also called alternative reality games, are the ones that take the essence of everyday life. In its depth, and through it, interaction with the real world and deepening of knowledge takes place. (Deterding et, 2011)

The basic idea of gamification is to use this motivational power for games for other purposes that are not only related to the recreational purposes of the game itself. gamification environments are currently used for various goals such as improving learning in schools and training, or influencing behavior. gamefication by computers and technology used to influence the motivations and behavior of individuals through Game-like systems. This is due to the general prevalence of technological games in contemporary society, and it is believed that individuals who increasingly participate in play-supported activities are likely to stimulate their state of motivation. Therefore, the use of computer technologies in changing human behavior aims to teach, organize, support and motivate training activities by providing Best practices. (Hamari & Koivisto, 2014)

Some applications of gamification have positive effects in terms of enhancing motivation and learning as learning by gamification affect the participants in a real way, as the integration between the elements inspired by the game goes beyond the superficial and focuses on the deeper structural considerations of the games such as challenge, sense of control, and decision-making. That gamification leads to the achievement of self-regulation

for students by providing opportunities to perform self-censorship, which sets clear expectations for the learner. Gamification is constantly promoting, problem-solving which can help in strengthening students' motivation to learn. (Gressick & Langston, 2017)

Mathematics' Curricula have developed at an accelerated pace in bringing together the countries of the world in recent years, and mathematics has enjoyed a large share of these developments due to the special importance of these developments in mathematics curricula because of its special importance due to its participation in all life activities, so researchers expanded in designing and building modern curricula that It is based on the theories of learning and learners' activity and their participation in developing concepts, and since mathematics is an accumulative science based on rules that went through many eras, there were special difficulties for learning that subject and it became an intellectual subject requiring a diversity of thinking, methods and advanced teaching strategies. (Thallab and Omar, 2013)

Mathematical skills are activities with range from mere application of the rule to actions that require linking processes higher than the previous procedural level, and they require accuracy, understanding and speed in performance. skills are divided into two types: manual skills: such as drawing and measurement, and academic mental skills: such as application and solving equations. (Hemdan, 2010)

Technological change has imposed on educational and educational institutions interest in providing students with thinking skills and knowledge that are compatible with the requirements of the future to prepare a generation capable of playing positive roles in society and such goals require a change in the school's functions and the role of the teacher and the student so that this is in line with the goals of learning new mathematics that are no longer He is limited to number and form, but has become a study of pattern and relationship. The student is no longer a passive recipient, but rather an actor who builds mathematical information on his own to fit with the student's cognitive environment in which he invests his innate and acquired abilities and moves from it towards creativity. (Al- rabey, 2020)

From the standpoint of the effectiveness of the gamification strategy and its relationship to achievement, motivation, and the importance of applying modern technological strategies and tools in teaching students to mathematics skills, the importance of study and the results it can reach is crystallized.

1.2 Study problem:

Internet network is considered one of the most important technological innovations that it has been shown to be great in many fields, and it is very special in the educational field. E-learning tools are also considered among the most important educational technological applications of the Internet. They are agents of the traditional material environment by using the capabilities of information and communication technology to design, develop, manage and evaluate different learning processes.

Learning strategies and methods are devised to advocate for e-learning, so that many educational strategies and methods can be presented and used in these environments. Learning strategies that have achieved remarkable success in e-learning settings Gamification strategy. (Al amir, 2019)

One of the goals of teaching mathematics courses is to develop the minimum cognitive mathematics skills (Al-Mahdi, 2005), which are remembering, understanding and application, and the higher goals, which include analysis, synthesis and evaluation, and thus the student moves from learning the physical and semi-perceptible to the abstract. Therefore, developing cognitive skills requires the use of interactive teaching strategies (Al-Mutawa, 2018), including the gamification strategy, effective teaching of mathematics requires planning a set of activities and managing the classroom environment, and the use of active learning strategies in learning and teaching mathematics in all stages of education occurs in deeper learning and higher achievement and stimulates better recall by students as it develops higher thinking skills among students. And the formation of a special understanding of mathematics for students. (Balawi, 2019)

Many studies have confirmed the effectiveness of the gamification strategy on improving the academic performance of students in various stages of education, including (Shaheen, 2020) and (Al-Shammari, 2019), which linked the effectiveness of the strategy of gamification and the development of motivation and (Al-Zein, 2019) and (Abdul Hamid & Abu Bakr& Yahya, 2018), (Al-Qazzaz, 2018) and (Qarni & Abu Saif, 2016) which confirm the positive result of using gamification strategy in teaching Mathematical skills.

Accordingly, the study's problematic and its main questions are about **what is The impact of using electronic gamafication on the performance and Mathematical skills of Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University High Schools students from teachers points of views?**

1.3: Study question:

- 1- What is the most important digital applications that employ the foundations and principles of gamification in the teaching and learning process?
- 2- What is the basic Mathematics learning skills for secondary stage can use E- gaming?
- 3- What is the trend of mathematics teachers towards the use of electronic gamification applications in teaching the subject?
- 4- What are the difficulties of employing electronic applications of the strategy of gamification in teaching mathematics?

- 5- What is the effect of using gamification application on students' performance and basic mathematics learning skills?

1.4: Study Objective:

- 1- Discuss concept, forms, components and objectives of gamification application in education.
- 2- Discuss the Standards governing electronic activities based on the strategy of gamification?
- 3- Show the most important digital applications that employ the foundations and principles of gamification in the teaching and learning process.
- 4- Determine the general objectives of teaching mathematics in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
- 5- Determine the basic Mathematics learning skills for secondary stage can use E- gaming.
- 6- Clarify trends of mathematics teachers towards the use of electronic gamification applications in teaching the subject?
- 7- clarify the difficulties of employing electronic applications of the strategy of gamification in teaching mathematics.
- 8- Reach the effect of using e-gamification on students' performance and basic mathematics learning skills.

1.5: Study importance:

Education strategies have evolved and changed thanks to the technical and programmatic revolution, whose applications have found wide resonance in the education process, and then traditional education has become a barrier to developing basic skills for science education, especially mathematics. Hence, the importance of study can be explained as follows:

Theoretical significance

- 1- The study is useful in clarifying the concept, objectives, patterns and forms of applying the strategy of gamification in the education process with an explanation of the advantages and possibilities.
- 2 - The study is useful in identifying the most important electronic applications that the teacher can benefit from in applying the electronic gamification strategy in teaching mathematics.
- 3- The study is useful in identifying the difficulties, obstacles and caveats of applying the online gamification strategy in acquiring mathematics skills?
- 4- The study is useful in identifying attitudes of mathematics teachers at the secondary level towards employing electronic gamification applications in teaching mathematics.
- 5- The study helps in identifying and explaining the skills that mathematics education through the electronic gamification strategy contributes to its development.

Applied importance:

- 1- The study is useful in coming up with recommendations that enhance the existence of electronic applications for electronic gamification specialized in teaching mathematics.
- 2- The study is useful in shedding light on the difficulties and obstacles of using electronic gamification applications in teaching mathematics and thus overcoming them.
- 3- The study concludes with the determination of the impact and the importance of employing electronic gamification applications in acquiring mathematics skills.

1.6: Study limits:

Objective limits: Determining the impact of using electronic gamification on the performance and mathematics skills of Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University High Schools students from teachers points of views.

Human Limits: The study will be applied to mathematics teachers of Princess Nora University High Schools students

limits boundaries: The study was applied during the first semester of 1442

1.7: Study terminology:

Gamification strategy:

It is mechanical uses based on the principle of play, aesthetics, and many methods such as thinking and problem solving through play, in order to involve the largest number of students and motivate them and raise their motivation to work and encourage them towards learning. (Al Nady,2020 :7)

Procedurally:

It is the use of playing through electronic games applications as a method of acquiring mathematical concepts and building skills of remembering, analysis, problem-solving and decision-making.

Mathematic:

They are symbols, numbers, and material things, and a separate or connected quantity or amount, and studying them in the elementary journey helps the pupil to understand and use different methods to install mathematical concepts in the mind, including arithmetic (comparison - counting - arrangement - geometric shapes - space - measurement. (Musharakah, 2014: 11)

Mathematical skills

Skill:

It is the ability to perform a task with speed, mastery and accuracy, and the skill is the perception or cognitive processes such as remembering, analyzing, synthesizing, clarifying and discovering logical errors when they are easy, but if they are complex, such as making decisions or solving problems, then they are called strategies. Learning mathematical skills plays an important role in learning mathematics because If students do not acquire some skills in mathematics, this restricts their progress in learning mathematics, and this work is often linked to an algorithm that determines the method of work and its procedures. Different types of speed and mastery. (Khalaf, 2008)

Procedurally:

The mathematical concepts and skills of remembering, analysis, problem-solving and decision-making that students acquire through the use of play using electronic games applications

Academic performance:

it is the learning outcome or the extent to which the student achieves the desired educational goals. (Shahin,2020 : 860)

2: Theoretical framework

2.1 Previous Studies:

- The study of (El nady, 2020), aimed to identify the importance of the use of gamification in developing creative thinking skills for third-grade students in the basic subject of science. To achieve the goal of the study, the quasi-experimental approach was used by conducting the Torrance Test for Creative Thinking verbally and it was applied to a sample consisting of 134 male and female students, and the number of students in the experimental sample reached 68 students and the control group, 66. The study concluded that there were statistically significant differences in the overall performance and in all creative thinking skills in favor of the experimental group. Therefore, the study recommended the use of gamification in teaching science.
- According to (Shaheen, 2020), the study aimed to identify the effectiveness of the gamification strategy in managing the learning environment and improving the teaching performance of students in the basic education stage. The study indicates the effectiveness of the gamification strategy designed by electronic application in managing the classroom and extra-curricular learning environment and improving the academic performance of the study individuals.
- According to (Al-Ghamdi, 2019), the study aimed to identify the effectiveness of learning gamification in developing motivation towards mathematics among sixth-grade pupils of primary school in the city of Makkah Al-Mukarramah. To achieve the aim of the study, the semi-experimental approach and the motivation measure towards learning mathematics were used, and the study sample consisted of (57) female students, who were divided into two groups: an experimental group (28) female students, taught using learning gamification, and a control group (29) female students. Teaching it in the usual way, and the results of the research reached: There are differences between the mean scores of the experimental and control groups in the post-measurement of the measure of motivation towards learning mathematics at dimensions: challenge, enjoyment of learning, confidence and self-efficacy, and the overall score, in favor of the experimental group. The magnitude of the impact of learning gamification in developing motivation towards learning mathematics was significant for all dimensions individually and for the overall degree.
- According to (Al-Juhani, 2018), the study aimed to develop the mathematical problem-solving skills of talented students in the first grade of secondary school through digitally playing education with the blackboard. To achieve the goal of the study, the experimental method was used and the experimental group numbered 16 students and officers with 20 students, and the study found differences Statistical significance in favor of the experimental group in the post-measurement of mathematics problem-solving skills, and thus the effectiveness of learning gamification through the blackboard was proven to develop problem-solving skills in mathematics
- According to (Al-Hefnawi, 2017), the study aimed to identify the effect of using electronic activities based on gamification in light of the criteria for developing mathematical concepts among deaf students with learning difficulties. To achieve the goal of the study, the experimental method was used and the study was applied to an experimental and controlled sample of 30 male and female students. The study indicated that there were statistically significant differences in the level of achievement of mathematical concepts in favor of the experimental group.
- According to (Al-Warikat and Shawwa, 2016), the study aimed to identify the effect of teaching mathematics with the strategy of learning by playing in acquiring mathematical skills and improving social communication skills among first-grade students in Jordan. To achieve the goal of the study, the experimental approach was used on an experimental sample. Controls with a number of 26 each, and a test was used to measure mathematical skills, and the study found statistically significant differences in favor of the post-test and on the communication scale in favor of the post-test.

Comments on previous studies

We agree with the study (Alnady, 2020), which emphasized the importance of the strategy of gamification in the development of creative thinking, and we agree with what was confirmed by the study (Shaheen, 2020) on the impact of the strategy of gamification on achieving learning goals and raising the level of teaching performance of the teacher, and we rely on what the study (Al-Ghamdi, 2019) of the impact of gamification strategy on learning motivation for mathematics and its effect on the level of acquired skills, and we agree with the findings of the study (Al-Juhani, 2018) on the impact of gamification strategy on developing the skill of solving mathematical problems. The impact of gamification strategy on developing mathematical concepts. (Al-Warikat and Shawwa, 2016) also confirmed the effect of gamification strategy on possessing mathematical skills.

2.2: Theoretical framework:

Gamification are one of the purposeful activities that can be used in teaching mathematics, which can be defined as a purposeful activity that includes specific actions that the teacher and students perform by following certain rules because of their many and multiple advantages to serve the emotional and cognitive goals where the teacher can employ them in facing problems Educational and educational, especially the individual differences between learners, and to provide knowledge, information and skills by presenting them in a format that is likable to students. (Al-Hefnawy, 2017)

The concept and history of gamification:

In (2010), the use of the term gamification, the game, or the game became universally popular, but this does not mean the absence of the idea of gamification before, and he mentions the first beginnings of the emergence and development of digital games dating back to the late 1960s, which witnessed the emergence of the first computer games. (Sanchez, 2011) has pointed out that the recent tremendous advances in computers, communication technologies, and the Internet have made it possible to design and produce digital games rich in multimedia with the highest level of interactivity and to benefit from them in enhancing the teaching process.

Digital gamification appears in three forms:

The first approach: in which the digital game is a goal in itself, where the student plays the role of the game designer and has to be familiar with the knowledge, skills and programming languages in order to design the game.

The second approach: in which games are designed and integrated in the learning context, meaning that they are an educational medium that serves the learning objectives.

The third approach: in which games are used in the evaluation process, and it is the most cost-effective approach in terms of money and time and can be used with any field and applied to any learner.

E- Gamification in education and its components

Kapp (2012) identified a set of principles of gamification in student learning, making the points that students collect as a phased reinforcer for him to accomplish a specific task and designing electronic activity that includes the principle of gamification in a gradual manner, so that it starts from easy to Difficult, from simple to complex, with the possibility of returning levels to emphasize the skill or develop it, or make a board for the distinguished participants in a particular stage, or even the whole game.

Oblinger (2006) noted that gamification supports pedagogical principles

The following:

1- Capacity-building: it fosters different learners' decisions, and includes levels commensurate with all individual differences.

2- Feedback: It provides immediate feedback during learning sessions based on gamification.

2- Active learning: Gamification is designed to involve the learner in discoveries that promote the principle of active learning.

4- Motivation: learners are involved in searching for the goal of the game or gamification, and achieving it.

5- Social Dimension: Most of the games are multiplayer, social, and so is gaming.

-6 Help: There are different challenges within the game that allow a little help to overcome them.

7- Transfer: The gamification principle promotes the transfer of learning from a game context to a real learning context.

8- Evaluation: Players can evaluate knowledge or skill acquired through comparison with other players, Likewise, gamification assesses their skills.

The principle of gamification helps students develop their various skills. It is a method Through it the student discovers multiple and varied opportunities to discover things. Through gamification, the student interacts with all his senses with the skill; he hears, sees and touches, and all skills that is presented to the student that can be transformed into a game that adopts the principle of gamification, through which the student learns different skills, and is equipped with a collection of facts and knowledge in a way that increases his motivation and makes him enjoy. (Al nady , 2020)

Goals of gamification in education:

gamification has different goals and includes many aspects of it

Cognitive goals: developing mental capacities, thinking, exploration and innovation.

Social goals: communicate with others, learn social rules, rules and regulations.

Emotional goals: enhancing motivation, self-expression, character formation.

Skill objectives: Learn the skills of speed, accuracy, and problem solving.

Regardless of the audience or topic, the researcher believes that the main goal of gamification an environment Education is the creation of exciting educational and entertainment content, and it is not intended to transform the educational process into a game, but to have a drive to compete, improve oneself, and excel over others, and that there are satisfactory and motivating rewards for that. (Alghamdy, 2020)

Standards governing electronic activities based on the strategy of gamification:

For educational activity based on gamification to have an impact, it must comply with a number of criteria, namely:

- 1- The connection of the games with the special educational goals that the teacher strives to achieve.
- 2- These activities are suitable for students 'age and mental development level.
- 3- That this activity helps the learner to meditate, observe, balance and arrive at the facts in a logical way
- 4- The activities are free from any risks or downsides.
- 5- That these activities help the teacher through feedback that helps him / her to evaluate the skills that have been acquired, weaknesses and methods of dealing with them.
- 6- That the games relate to the learning environment.
- 7- The rules of the game should be easy, clear and uncomplicated.
- 8- The game is exciting and fun.
- 9- To be suitable for the experiences, abilities and preferences of the pupils.
- 10- The game gives students a sense of freedom and independence. (Al- Hefnawy, 2017)

Applications that employ the foundations and principles of gamification in the teaching and learning process:

1-ClassDojo: an application that helps teachers manage classrooms by recording the positive and negative behaviors of each student and sharing them with parents. It is characterized by its use of symbols for fun and loving cartoon characters for the learner.

2-Duolingo: a very fun application to learn different languages, by collecting points for students, in order to move to higher levels.

3- Quiz - Quizizz: A site that allows teachers to turn educational activities into fun activities and quizzes, and share them with other educators.

4- Kahoot: A site that allows teachers to transform scholarly assignments into fun games and challenges, that students implement during a specific time, and it also provides teachers with the ability to follow pupils' reactions during and after the game.

5-Classcraft: a site that allows teachers to change the way of teaching to a collective role-playing style, where students assume different personalities and form teams, and each team seeks to complete the educational mission and obtain additional points, in order to defeat other teams and qualify for higher levels.(Shahin, 2020)

General objectives of teaching mathematics in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia:

- 1- Providing students with the opportunity to practice sound ways of thinking such as inductive, deductive and contemplative thinking
- 2- Providing students with skills in using problem-solving method.
- 3- Emphasizing the importance of mathematics in our public life, by helping students learn about the impact of mathematics on civilized development.
- 4- Providing the student with the necessary skills to understand what he is studying and to uncover new relationships.
- 5- Helping the student to form sound tendencies and attitudes towards mathematics and to taste it.
- 6- Helping the student to rely on himself in achieving mathematics.
- 7- The development of some healthy habits such as accuracy, order, cooperation, mutual respect and criticism
- 8- Building the development of mental skills and scientific innovations.
- 9- Emphasizing that mathematics is the mother of science.
- 10- Highlighting the role and contributions of Arab Muslims in the emergence of mathematics.(Rezk, 2018)

Mathematics learning skills

The mathematics curriculum has general goals that it seeks to achieve through teaching mathematics in all stages from kindergarten to university education, which are represented in: acquiring scientific and thinking skills, dealing with knowledge of a digital nature, in addition to appreciating the impact and importance of mathematics. In developing society, forming positive and sound tendencies and attitudes towards learning mathematics by the learner, and acquiring good social skills. (Al wrikat & shawa, 2016)

The basic mathematics skills for the secondary stage:

- 1- Determine true and false values in mathematical conditional statements.
- 2- Proving the correctness of mathematical expressions by inductive and deductive justification through the law of logical separation and the law of syllogism.
- 3- Writing a mathematical proof using free proof, geometric proof, and serial proof.
- 4- Finding the slope of a line, writing the equation of a straight line, and the geometric relationships between lines.
- 5- Prove the congruence of triangles using cases
- 6- Create bisectors in the triangle and the mid-cut and highs.
- 7- Indirect proof, the construct of a triangle, and inequalities in two triangles.
- 8- Find the sum of the interior and exterior angles of a polygon.
- 9- Compare quadrilaterals
- 10- Prove the similarity of triangles using cases
- 11- Solve problems with proportion and proportion.
- 12- Draw pictures of shapes for engineering reflection, withdrawal, rotation and expansion
- 13- Installation of geometric transformations algebraically and graphically.
- 14- Find the measurements of the central and inscribed angles and areas of circular sectors
- 15- Finding circuit equations.
- 16- Writing functions and representing them graphically.
- 17- Representation of linear inequalities and absolute value inequalities
- 18- Matrix concept and mathematical operations on it.
- 19- Matrix concept and mathematical processes.
- 20- Perform operations on complex numbers.
- 21- Solving quadratic equations by general law
- 22- Finding and distinguishing inverse relations and the inverse function.
- 23- Perform mathematical operations on rational expressions
- 24- Distinguish the problems of direct, combined, inverse, and compound change.
- 25- Proof of mathematical sentences using mathematical induction. (Education Skills Guide for Secondary Education, 2020)

3. Research methodology

3.1 Introduction:

To achieve the aim of the study, the descriptive and analytical approach will be used. "The descriptive approach is concerned with collecting data and facts, classifying them and classifying them, in addition to careful in-depth analysis to arrive at generalizations about the subject of the study." (Saber and Khafaja, 2002, 87)

3.2 Participants:

Study community:

The study population determined with the mathematics teachers at Princess Nora University High Schools in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

The study sample

The researcher determine the study sample with 169 teachers for the mathematics as a random sample.

3.3 Data collection instrument

Study tool

After reviewing the literature and previous studies related to the subject of the study, the researcher design a questionnaire for the study sample.

The study tool reviewed by (Arbitrators) and the required amendment were done.

The study tool applied to Initial sample with (30) individual to test the reliability Alpha Cronbach and the required amendment were done.

3.4 Reliability:

To test the reliability Alpha Cronbach and the required amendment were done.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.876	20

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

The Cronbach alpha coefficient reached 0.876, which is an acceptable percentage of stability, as the ratio exceeds 0.6 Therefore, the questionnaire can be relied upon to achieve the study objectives.

3.5 Validity Statistics:

The study tool applied to Initial sample with (30) individual to test the results of the study.

3.6 Data collection procedures:

To apply the limits of the study, and to answer its questions, the following steps will be taken:

1. Previous studies and research in this field, whether they are Arab or foreign, reviewed.
2. The study tool identified and prepared, which is the questionnaire.

3. The questionnaire distributed to the study sample during the first semester of 1442 through electronic distribution
4. Results monitored and analyzed.

3.7 Data analysis:

Depending on the nature of the research and the goals seeks to achieve, the data analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program and Microsoft excel the results extracted according to the following statistical methods:

1. Frequencies and percentages: to know the characteristics of the individuals of the research sample.
2. Standard deviations and variance : To calculate the means of the questionnaire statements.
3. Cronbach's alpha coefficient: to calculate the reliability of the questionnaire.
4. The degree of response was determined to give a score (5) for the response strongly agree, and (4) for the response agree, and (3) for the response is neutral, (2) for the response is not in agreement, and (1) for the response strongly disagrees.

4.Results and Discussion

4.1Results of the Study

The questionnaire was presented to mathematics teachers at Princess Nora University High Schools in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia as our study community members through Electronic questionnaire. This part outlines the most important result of the questionnaire that is given us about the point of view of using the gamification application in teaching mathematics. All the tables below presents that most of the questions included in the questionnaire were answered accurately by all the participants of the study.

Furthermore, it shows the teachers community members points of view about The importance of using gamification application. For this reason, every researcher begins to analyze the statements included in the survey precisely in order to answer the questions of the study.. The tables below present and indicate the results for each phrase .

First: Standard deviation and variance

Rank	Statements	S.D	variance
1	gaming electronic applications are useful in teaching mathematics thanks to the possibilities of interaction.	.910	.827
2	I think it is effective to use electronic gamification applications to teach mathematical skills	.910	.828
3	The use of electronic gaming applications needs to have suitable software for learning the mathematics, which may not be readily available.	.966	.934
4	There is an effective use of electronic gamification applications in teaching mathematics on the skill of solving mathematical problems.	.980	.961
5	Training courses must be conducted to train the teacher in the use of electronic gaming applications and how to benefit from them.	1.001	1.002
6	I have the ability to employ e-gamification applications in teaching mathematics skills to high school students	1.010	1.020
7	There is an effective use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics on the skill of remembering and acquiring mathematical concepts.	1.017	1.034
8	Using electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics helps to achieve the Mathematical logical skill.	1.020	1.041
9	There is an effective application of electronic gamification in teaching mathematics skill of analysis and discovery of logical errors.	1.044	1.89
10	The employment of electronic gaming applications in mathematics education increases the level of enthusiasm and motivation to learn the material	1.049	1.100
11	gaming electronic applications are useful in teaching mathematics thanks to correction capabilities.	1.067	1.138
12	Using electronic applications in teaching English saves the teacher's time and effort.	1.071	1.147
13	There is an effectiveness of employing applications of electronic gamification in teaching mathematics on the skill of students in decision-making	1.078	1.162
14	You can't rely only on gamification apps to teach mathematics	1.102	1.214
15	The curriculum may not be compatible with the teaching of the	1.105	1.221

	English mathematics with the possibilities of application and the scientific material in it.		
16	The use of gaming electronic applications in teaching the mathematics requires a special skill for the student that needs training.	1.137	1.292
17	The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics requires a stable connection to the Internet.	1.150	1.321
18	The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics helps to raise the level of students' achievement of mathematics.	1.150	1.322
19	There are no reliable electronic gaming applications for learning mathematics from the Ministry of Education for language teaching.	1.179	1.390
20	The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics requires an additional cost to teach the mathematics, either for the application or for connecting to the network.	1.203	1.447

Table 2: Standard deviation and variance

Second: Frequency statistics:

The first statement: : I have the ability to employ e-gamification applications in teaching mathematics skills to high school students

Figure1: I have the ability to employ e-gamification applications in teaching mathematics skills to high school students.

The above chart showed that the majority with 45 % agreed that have the ability to employ e-gamification applications in teaching mathematics skills to high school students, 26.6% strongly agree, then 16% were neutral, 10.1% were not agree, 2.4% strongly disagree.

Figure 2 I think it is effective to use electronic gamification applications to teach mathematical skills

The above chart showed that that the majority with 42.6 % agreed that think it is effective to use electronic gamification applications to teach mathematical skills, 39.1% were strongly agree, 12.4% neutral, 4.1% not agree, 1.8% strongly dis agree.

Figure 3 You can't rely only on gamification apps to teach mathematics.

The above chart showed that that the majority with 40.2% strongly agree that can't rely only on gamification apps to teach mathematics, 25.4% agreed that , 23.7% neutral, 7.7% not agree, 3% strongly disagree.

Figure 4: Using electronic applications in teaching English saves the teacher's time and effort.

The above chart showed that that the majority with 33.7% agreed that using electronic applications in teaching English saves the teacher's time and effort., 32% strongly agree, 21.3% neutral, 10.7% not agree, 2.4% strongly disagree.

Figure 5 :The employment of electronic gaming applications in mathematics education increases the level of enthusiasm and motivation to learn the material.

The above chart showed that that the majority with 37.3% agreed that the employment of electronic gaming applications in mathematics education increases the level of enthusiasm and motivation to learn the material, 33.7% strongly agree, 20.1% neutral, 4.7% not agree, 4.1% strongly disagree.

Figure 6: gaming electronic applications are useful in teaching mathematics thanks to the possibilities of interaction.

The above chart showed that that the majority with 47.9% agreed that gaming electronic applications are useful in teaching mathematics thanks to the possibilities of interaction., 30.2%strongly agree, 14.8% neutral, 5.3% not agree, 1.8% dis agree.

Figure 7: gaming electronic applications are useful in teaching mathematics thanks to correction capabilities..

The above chart showed that that the majority with 38.5% agreed that gaming electronic applications are useful in teaching mathematics thanks to correction capabilities., 34.3% strongly agree,17.8% neutral, 4.7% not agree, 4.7% strongly disagree.

Figure 8: The use of gaming electronic applications in teaching the mathematics requires a special skill for the student that needs training..

The above chart showed that that the majority with 31.4% strongly agreed with the use of gaming electronic applications in teaching the mathematics requires a special skill for the student that needs training.,30.8% agree, 20.7% neutral, 14.2% not agree, 3% strongly dis agree.

Figure 9: Using electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics helps to achieve the Mathematical logical skill..

Using electronic applications in teaching English helps to achieve the correct pronunciation of the language.

The above chart showed that that the majority with 40.8% strongly agreed with using electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics helps to achieve the Mathematical logical skill., 29.6% agree, 22.5% neutral, 4.7% not agree, 2.4% strongly dis agree.

Figure 10: The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics helps to raise the level of students' achievement of mathematics.

The use of electronic applications in teaching English helps to raise the level of students' achievement of basic grammar.

The above chart showed that the majority with 37.9% agreed with the use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics helps to raise the level of students' achievement of mathematics., 32% strongly agree, 18.9% neutral, 3.6% not agree, 7.7% strongly disagree.

Figure 11: The use of electronic gaming applications needs to have suitable software for learning the mathematics, which may not be readily available.

The use of electronic applications needs to have suitable software for learning the language, which may not be readily available.

The above chart showed that the majority with 42% agreed that the use of electronic gaming applications needs to have suitable software for learning the mathematics, which may not be readily available., 29% strongly agree, 18.9% neutral, 8.9% not agree, 1.2% strongly disagree.

Figure 12: The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics requires a stable connection to the Internet.

The above chart showed that the majority with 42% strongly agreed that The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics requires a stable connection to the Internet., 34.3% agree, 10.7% neutral, 7.7% not agree, 5.3% strongly disagree.

Figure 13: The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics requires an additional cost to teach the mathematics, either for the application or for connecting to the network..

The above chart showed that the majority with 33.7% agreed that the use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics requires an additional cost to teach the mathematics, either for the application or for connecting to the network., 32,5% agree, 14,2% neutral, 14,8% not agree, 4,7% strongly disagree.

Figure 14: The curriculum may not be compatible with the teaching of the English mathematics with the possibilities of application and the scientific material in it.

The above chart showed that the majority with 35.5% agreed that the curriculum may not be compatible with the teaching of the English mathematics with the possibilities of application and the scientific material in it., 26.6% were neutral, 21.9% strongly agree, 10.7% not agree, 5.3% strongly disagree.

Figure 15: There are no reliable electronic gaming applications for learning mathematics from the Ministry of

Education for language teaching.

The above chart showed that the majority with 37.3% agreed that there are no reliable electronic gaming applications for learning mathematics from the Ministry of Education for language teaching., 23.7% strongly agree, 16.6% neutral, 17.2% disagree, 5.3% strongly disagree.

Figure 16: Training courses must be conducted to train the teacher in the use of electronic gaming applications

and how to benefit from them.

The above chart showed that the majority with 45.6% strongly agreed training courses must be conducted to train the teacher in the use of electronic gaming applications and how to benefit from them., 32% were agreed, 12.4% neutral, 9.5% not agree, 0.6% strongly disagree.

Figure 17: There is an effectiveness of employing applications of electronic gamification in teaching mathematics on the skill of students in decision-making.

New applications for learning English must be designed under the Ministry of Education and can be used in teaching the curriculum.

New applications for learning English must be designed under the Ministry of Education and can be used in teaching the curriculum.

The above chart showed that the majority with 47.3% strongly agreed that there is an effectiveness of employing applications of electronic gamification in teaching mathematics on the skill of students in decision-making, 29% were agreed, 12.4%, 8.9% not agree, 2.4% strongly disagree.

Figure 18: There is an effective use of electronic gamification applications in teaching mathematics on the skill

A training part supervised by the teacher must be included for the student to acquire the ability to use applications in learning the English language.

A training part supervised by the teacher must be included for the student to acquire the ability to use applications in learning the English language.

of solving mathematical problems.

The above chart showed that that the majority with 40.2% strongly agreed that There is an effective use of electronic gamification applications in teaching mathematics on the skill of solving mathematical problems., 34.9% were agreed, 16.6% neutral, 7.1% not agree, 1.2% strongly dis agree.

Figure 19: There is an effective application of electronic gamification in teaching mathematics skill of analysis and discovery of logical errors.

Attention must be paid to interactive and e-learning for its effectiveness in raising the level of achievement in learning the English language.

Attention must be paid to interactive and e-learning for its effectiveness in raising the level of achievement in learning the English language.

The above chart showed that that the majority with 38.5% agreed that there is an effective application of electronic gamification in teaching mathematics skill of analysis and discovery of logical errors., 36.7% strongly agreed, 17.2% neutral, 3% not agree, 4.7% strongly dis agree.

Figure 20: There is an effective use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics on the skill of remembering and acquiring mathematical concepts.

The above chart showed that the majority with 43.2% strongly agreed that there is an effective use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics on the skill of remembering and acquiring mathematical concepts, 32.5% were agreed, 17.2% were neutral, 4.1% not agree, 3% strongly disagree.

Results & Conclusion:

There was homogeneity between the study sample beginning with that gaming electronic applications are useful in teaching mathematics thanks to the possibilities of interaction. Which agree with (Al- ameshat, 2019) and (Al shemary, 2019) With S.D (.910) then think it is effective to use electronic gaming applications to teach mathematical skills with S.D (.910) then the use of electronic gaming applications needs to have suitable software for learning the mathematics, which may not be readily available with S.D (.966) then There is an effective use of electronic gamification applications in teaching mathematics on the skill of solving mathematical problems with S.D (.980)

Training courses must be conducted to train the teacher in the use of electronic gaming applications and how to benefit from them. with S.D (1.001) then have the ability to employ e-gamification applications in teaching mathematics skills to high school students with S.D (1.101) then there is an effective use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics on the skill of remembering and acquiring mathematical concepts with S.D (1.017) then using electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics helps to achieve the Mathematical logical skill. With S.D (1.020) then there is an effective application of electronic gamification in teaching mathematics skill of analysis and discovery of logical errors with S.D (1.044).

The employment of electronic gaming applications in mathematics education increases the level of enthusiasm and motivation to learn the material was with S.D (1.049) which agree with (Al- Amir , 2019) then gaming electronic applications are useful in teaching mathematics thanks to correction capabilities. With S.D (1.067) then Using electronic applications in teaching saves the teacher's time and effort. Which agree with (Shahin, 2020) With S.D (1.071) then there is an effectiveness of employing applications of electronic gamification in teaching mathematics on the skill of students in decision-making with S.D (1.078) then can't rely only on gamification apps to teach mathematics with S.D (1.102) then the curriculum may not be compatible with the teaching of the English mathematics with the possibilities of application and the scientific material in it with S.D (1.105).

The use of gaming electronic applications in teaching the mathematics requires a special skill for the student that needs training. Was with S.D (1.137) then The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics requires a stable connection to the Internet. With S.D (1.150) then The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics helps to raise the level of students' achievement of mathematics. Then There are no reliable electronic gaming applications for learning mathematics from the Ministry of Education for language teaching. With S.D (1.179) finally The use of electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics requires an additional cost to teach the mathematics, either for the application or for connecting to the network. With S.D (1.203).

There is agreement among mathematics teachers on the positive trend towards employing electronic gaming applications in teaching mathematics and acquiring skills of remembering, understanding, analysis, problem-solving and decision-making. Which agree with (Al- zain, 2019) Therefore, there is an effect of applying that strategy on the level of students' performance and mathematics skills, but they still have difficulties and obstacles represented in the necessity of having Training and qualification for both teacher and student, the presence of necessary tools such as applications and internet connection, in addition to the presence of applications commensurate with the educational goals established and belonging to the Ministry of Education so that the teacher can rely on them.

In general, employing electronic gaming applications helps students acquire mathematical concepts, remember and apply rules, overcome the difficulties of the subject and increase motivation towards it, solve the problem of individual differences between students and the existence of a positive motivation through the spirit of competition to learn skills.

Recommendations:

- 1- Create electronic gaming applications specialized in teaching mathematics.
- 2- Conducting training courses for teachers on methods of employing gamification in teaching mathematics
- 3- Conducting contests through playing between students to motivate them to learn mathematics through gamification
- 4- Creating an approved guide for the Ministry to apply gamification in mathematics

References

- Shaheen, Yasmine Mohamed Meligy (2020). The effectiveness of the gamification strategy in managing the learning environment and improving academic performance among basic education stage pupils, College of Education, Tanta University.
- Deterding, S., Khaled, R., Nacke, L., Dixon, D.(2011): From Game Design Elements to Gamefulness: Defining "Gamification", Proceedings of the MindTrek 2011, Tampere.
- Hamari, Juho & Koivisto, Jonna (2014):Measuring flow in gamification: Dispositional Flow Scale-2. Computers in Human Behavior 40, 133–143
- Gressick, J. & Langston, B. (2017): The Guided Classroom: Using Gamification to Engage and Motivate Undergraduates, Journal of the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning, Vol. 17, No. 3, July, pp. 109-123. doi:10.14434/josotl.v17i3.22119
- Al Amir, Laila Helmy Al-Ajami (2019). Designing an electronic learning environment based on the gamification strategy and its impact on developing the web development skills of high school students and their motivation to learn, Damietta University Master Thesis.
- Qarni, Osama Mahmoud and Abu Seif, Mahmoud Sayed (2016). A proposed model for using gamification in Egyptian universities, the twenty-third annual scientific conference of the Egyptian Association for Comparative Education and Educational Administration, Faculty of Education, Ain Shams University.
- Al-Qazzaz, Munther Adnan Muhammad (2018). The effectiveness of employing electronic games based on smart mobile phones in acquiring and retaining technological concepts for tenth grade students in Gaza, Master Thesis, College of Education, Islamic University of Gaza.
- Al-Zein, Hanan bint Asaad Hashem (2019). Effectiveness of a proposed educational program to develop the skills of designing and employing gamification among students of the Higher E-Learning Diploma and their perceptions towards it, The Educational Magazine, Issue Sixty-eighth
- Abdel Hamid, Ibrahim Youssef and Abu Bakr, Qassi and Aaron (2018). The Impact of gamification Learner-Centered Education on Teaching Arabic to Speakers of Other Languages, ASEAN Comparative Education Research Journal on Islam and Civilization (ACER-J) Volume 2 (2) September 2018, 18-38. eISSN: 2600-769X.
- Al-Shammari, Badr Tharwi Abdullah (2019). The Effectiveness of Using Gamification in Developing Motivation to Learn English Language Among High School Students in Hail, Journal of the College of Education, Assiut University, Volume 35, Issue 5
- Al-Thallab, Saeed Hassan, Ali, Omar, Tahani Ghalib (2013). The Effect of a Strategy (Think, Pair, Share) in the achievement of second-grade intermediate students in mathematics and their inferential thinking, Journal of Adab Al-Farahidi, Issue 17.
- Al-Rubaie, Farah Muhammad Reda Hamza (2020). The role of mathematics teachers in developing creative thinking skills, Journal of Arts, Literature, Humanities and Sociology, No. 57.
- Al-Balawi, Aayed bin Ali Muhammad (2019). The degree to which faculty members in the Department of Mathematics at the College of Science at Taibah University use active learning strategies from their point of view, Journal of Mathematics Education, Volume 22 Issue 4 April 2019, Part One.
- Al-Mutawa, Intisar Abdul Aziz Ibrahim (2018). The Effectiveness of Using Smart Devices in the Development of Differentiated Teaching Practices for Pre-Service Primary Mathematics Teachers, Journal of Educational Sciences, Issue 16, Imam Muhammad bin Saud Islamic University.
- Abdul-Mahdi, Muhammad Ahmad Diab (2005) The effect of the learning mastery strategy in teaching mathematics on the cognitive and emotional levels among tenth grade female students in Jerusalem schools, a master's thesis, Deanship of Postgraduate Studies, Al-Quds University.

- Elnady, Hoda Gomaa Abbas (2020). The Effect of Using Gamification on the Development of Creative Thinking Skills for Third-Grade Students in the Science Subject in the Capital, Amman, Master Thesis, College of Educational Sciences, Middle East University.
- Al-Hefnawi, Mahmoud Muhammad (2017). The effect of using electronic activities based on the principle of gamification in light of standards for developing mathematical concepts among deaf pupils with learning difficulties, *Journal of Educational Sciences*, Fourth Issue, Part Three.
- Al-Ghamdi, and Wafa Saeed Ahmed (2019). The Effectiveness of Learning Gamification in Developing Motivation Towards Mathematics for Sixth Grade Pupils in Makkah Al-Mukarramah, *Journal of Scientific Research in Education*. P. 20, c. 4
- Al-Warikat, Aisha Abdullah and Al-Shawwa, Hala Hussein (2016). The Impact of Teaching Mathematics on the Learning-by-Play Strategy in Acquiring Mathematical Skills and Improving Social Communication Skills for First Grade Students in Jordan, *Journal of Educational Sciences*, Volume 43 Appendix 1
- Kapp, K.M. (2012). The gamification of learning and instruction, *Game-based Methods and Strategies for Training and Education*. Pfeiffer & Company.
- Oblinger, D. (2006). Games and learning. *Educause Quarterly Magazine*. (3). retrieved from: <https://www.educause.edu/library/eqm0630> [Accessed 05-04-2021].
- Rizk, Hanan bint Abdullah Ahmed (2018). The Impact of Real Learning on Developing Mathematical Thinking Skills among Middle School Students in Makkah Al-Mukarramah, *Journal of the College of Education, Al-Azhar University*, Issue: 180, Part Two.
- Al-Juhani, Zuhour Muhammad Suleiman (2018). The Impact of Teaching Gamification Through Blackboard to Develop Problem Solving Skills in Mathematics for Gifted Students in First Class of Secondary, *Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, Issue 19
- Education Skills Guide for Secondary Education, 2020 from: <https://eduschool40.blog/2020/12/03>
- Khalaf Sameh (2008). Mathematical skills, <https://www.teacher-sa.com/showthread.php?t=9332>
- Moshakra, Mofeda (2014). Problems of applying the mathematics curriculum for the first year of primary education in light of the approach to competencies, a master's thesis, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, University of Al-Arabi Bin Mahidi or Al-Bouaghi.
- Hemdan, Emad Eldin Awany (2010). The extent to which the mathematical concepts included in the mathematics books in Palestine NCTM conform to the higher basic stage with international standards, Master Thesis, College of Education, Al-Azhar University
- Alghamdy, Samia Fadel (2020). Systematic review of literary studies : education defect (2015 – 2019), *Arab Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences* Volume 4 Issue 17.
- Al-Ameshat, Bushra Yusef Ali (2019). The Effectiveness of Using (Todo Math) In Developing Of Creative Thinking Skills in the Primary School in Mathematics, Master Thesis, Middle East University.
- Al-shemary, Badr tharwy (2019). The effectiveness of using the gamification strategy in developing motivation towards learning the English language among secondary school students in Hail, *Journal of the Faculty of Education, Assiut University*, Volume 35, Issue 5
- Al – amir, Layla helmy Al agmy (2019). Designing an electronic learning environment based on the strategy of gamification and its impact on developing the skills of developing websites for high school students and their motivation to learn, a master's thesis, Faculty of Education, Damietta University.

Author Information

Dr. Mervat Abdullah Babeer

Assistant Professor of Teaching Technologies,
College of Education, Princess Nora bint
AbdulRahman University (PNU)
